
Future Power Systems – the importance and rationale of enforcing and segmenting the electrical energy grid

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Abstract— Most of today power systems are aiming to become a large synchronous system over a region which covers a big nation or union of nations. Europe is known as being a successful one-only synchronous system. India reached the same goal, while countries like USA and Japan are still segmented in more than one TSO controlled systems.

The paper investigates the architectures and rationale for a unique power system and analyses a vertically segmentation to allow resiliency and immunity at prosumer, building, neighbourhood and microgrid level, by using new technologies such as the solid-state transformer, hybrid inverters and DC busses to supply the resilient loads of the prosumers or of other aggregated local entities. For this, the paper presents an architecture which give progressively both advantages of large synchronous systems but also the resiliency needed at the level of end-users against local or general disturbances which can be propagated over the whole system.

Index Terms— Resilience, immunity, solid-state transformer, renewables, system stability

I. INTRODUCTION

MANY of today power systems are aiming to become huge synchronous systems over a big geographical region, usually having also a national or trans-national reason for being part of a certain geopolitical entity, aspiring for additional cohesion synergies.

This situation led to large synchronous systems which bring high local security of supply by quick power exchange support during temporary unbalances and access to a common energy market, for increasing competition and for decreasing the prices.

Europe is known as having a successful unique synchronous system integrated through ENTSO-E [1]. India reached recently the same goal under the slogan “One Nation One Grid” [2]. The strategy for a ultra high-voltage synchronous power

grid in China is also analysed in [3]. Countries such as USA and Japan are still segmented in two or more TSO based system and do not consider an imminent plan for a synchronous integration of the different power systems.

Between the reasons for pursuing the one-only synchronous power system can be pointed the fact that they better enable access to large energy markets, that they can reduce overall system services needs such as balancing services, as they can be shared by the different areas through the large grid and that different disturbances in generation of consumption are less severe over the whole system.

As a latest reason, the aim to highly increase the renewables penetration can better address their stochastic behaviour, as temporary reduction of renewable energy in one region can be covered by the energy transferred through the large synchronous system from another region, where renewable energy sources (RES) energy is more abundant.

While all these reasons are strong, there are also reasons to consider the need to diversify the architecture with multiple synchronous systems which interact asynchronously through back-to-back or similar solutions, in a different way than in the traditional horizontal interconnection.

II. POWER SYSTEMS ARCHITECTURES

This section considers the main architectures seen today for the AC power systems.

Figure 1 shows the traditional power system architecture of a country or of a region, presented as Sys_1 .

It can be seen that the whole system works as a synchronous grid, with a specific common frequency and with its classic measures to ensure the production and consumption equilibrium (primary f control, secondary f-P control, tertiary reserve, other means to ensure system stability).

The example shows how Sys_1 is synchronous coupled with Sys_2 and Sys_4 and how Sys_3 is completely decoupled for Sys_1 (no synchronous connection between them), thus in practice sometime having only a synchronous “island” with Sys_1 , fully decoupled from Sys_3 .

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Fig. 1. Classic country or regional power systems

An advancement from the classic power system is based on Flexible AC Transmission Systems (FACTS) technologies, as depicted in Fig. 2. In such systems, based on power electronics, different zones in the system have specific devices which enhance system controllability and power transfer capability [4][5]. The figure presents generically transversal FACTS resources T_{FACTS} , which are capable to increase system controllability and improve stability by injecting or consuming power in specific nodes and longitudinal FACTS devices L_{FACTS} , which allow system controllability by changing dynamically the equivalent impedances of the lines. The FACTS devices are also placed to increase power flow controllability between countries or zones which exchange energy, e.g. to better control the import or export of active energy between Sys_1, Sys_2 and Sys_3, which form grid loops. It may be necessary for instance to change the natural power flow of energy from Sys_1 to Sys_2 by reducing as much as possible the flow share through Sys_3, for reasons which have to do e.g. with transport fees or to capacity on tie-lines,

Fig. 2. Hybrid country or regional power systems

To be noted that FACTS technologies preserves the full AC behavior of the system, thus being considered as enhancers for a better use of an existing AC system, allowing sometimes to postpone other grid reinforcement decisions.

When much higher energy flow is needed between zones,

additional lines cannot be avoided.

There are limitations for the transfer of AC based energy on long distances which may ask for the use of DC lines. In crowded areas, such as in Europe, it starts to be also a fact that new corridors are difficult to be obtained, thus capacities cannot be increased easily as well, In this latest situation, conversion of an existing AC line (placed on an existing corridor) may be a solution for higher capacity, as capacity of a DC line can be higher than for an AC line.

Therefore, a further advancement is to hybridize the high voltage grid, which can be achieved with DC lines. Fig. 3 shows such DC lines to change artificially the power flow in the system Sys_1, while still keeping synchronous connection to Sys_2 and Sys_3.

In the Figure, Sys_4, which is not synchronously working with the other three systems, has two power connections, one with a DC line and another with a back-to-back connection. The back-to-back connection is an AC-DC and the DC-AC systems with a DC-bus-bar instead of a DC line.

Fig. 3. Hybrid country or regional power systems

The flexibility of hybrid systems is much increased, by helping energy transmission between AC points in a way which was not possible in AC paradigm alone, while keeping the whole system as one AC synchronous system, compatible with the already built distribution, down to the end-user socket. The additional back-to-back stations allow also energy interchange with systems which are not synchronous with the main zone (Sys_4 in Figure 3).

By combining FACTS technologies from Figure 2 and DC hybridization from Figure 3 we can get the modern AC power systems of today, as an example in Figure 4.

In this figure, by Sys_1 it is understood the entire synchronous system, either of a big nation or a union of nations, which uses FACTS and HVDC inside its grid and back-to-back devices to couple this system with other ones, non-synchronous with Sys_1, for different or equal nominal frequencies, but with a different operational control of each frequency f_2, f_3, f_4 .

Fig. 4. Complete compartmentation of power systems power systems

These are real enforcements of traditional AC grids, still keeping the original paradigm of having one large system based on synchronous connection, to remain compatible with the legacy AC distribution grid. Such large systems preserve the “one nation, one system” cohesion, as it is the case of the EU, Indian or hybrid Chinese systems.

While these systems bring more and more controllability, and provide a unitary view, local disturbances which were locally important become also less and less impactful within the large system. The common access brings also an important side effect: they become more and more exposed to big disturbances due to cascading effects [6]. It means that a disturbance which is not well mitigated can have impact at the whole network. The next sections give a glimpse of the potential effects and bring additional solutions to mitigate these situations.

III. DRAWBACKS OF FULLY SYNCHRONOUS SYSTEMS

As already described, many of today power systems are aiming to develop towards an integrated system over a large area, having important advantages to propel this vision. While these reasons are strong, there are also reasons to consider the need to keep multiple synchronous systems which interact asynchronously through back-to-back or similar solutions, as it has been also shown that it is the case between un-integrated power systems. In synchronized systems, even with well designed measures to keep system stability, an unexpected malfunction in the fully connected grid potentially may bring a cascade of dysfunctionalities – with a complexity which even cannot be well understood beforehand, and this becomes potentially a big vulnerability for the one system approach.

One comparison can be metaphorically made with the well known “Titanic fate”. Figure 5 shows the Titanic concept of security against major collision: the segmentation of the ship in many local compartments, such that a major problem anywhere will not affect the whole. The concept was considered so strong, that the ship was considered to be un-sinkable, because no water flow due to local collisions was able to affect other compartments, as the compartmentation was high enough to be over the normal water sea level.

Fig. 5. Titanic concept of security against disturbance: the major collision

The only connection was on much higher level, in the ship zone where water was impossible to travel through, due to gravity means.

The first and only travel showed that a cascading effect which was propagating exactly through the higher level became the main reason for Titanic sink. Figure 6 shows that after a certain local unbalance gave a tilt which allowed to fill with water additional compartments through the upper part, giving finally a propagation of the initial problem till the whole ship could be filled with water (which did not happen really because the ship broke anyhow at some moment).

Fig. 6. Compartments water filling due to upper part propagation vulnerability

The figure shows that the un-sinkable Titanic became vulnerable through the “disturbance” propagation at upper level, where there is no physical compartmentation. This suggests a comparison with the power systems which is vulnerable in any networks region, when the high voltage network has a progressive evolution of a disaster situation.

In order to prevent such drastic situations, complex conditions are asked to the connected generators, from strong nodes down to small ones [7]. This requests for keeping the system safe have therefore its payments, as the compatible RES and storage equipment need to be able to perform higher functionalities, thus being more expensive by themselves or by the costs of the needed approvals.

Malicious cyber-penetration on the SCADA/EMS of such large systems are also a general threat, as it can affect the whole system. New information technologies are needed to be developed in order to mitigate data inconsistencies in such systems and to develop countermeasures for the health of the entire grid, e.g. as developed in [8].

A radical paradigm change towards system segmentation is already sustained in studies [9][10], where fully hybrid systems using digital energy routers are proposed to be as the future architecture of power systems.

IV. SYSTEMS SEGMENTATION – LOOSELY COUPLED VERTICAL MULTI-SYNCHRONOUS AND HYBRID SYSTEMS

The paper is investigating solutions for preserving the advantages of large synchronous power systems while

providing possible architectures for strengthening the end-customer resiliency by proper segmenting the synchronous system, with more flexible interconnection on the high voltage system (horizontal dimension), while additional effective segmentation can be deployed on the vertical dimension of the same system, this being also the focus of the paper.

On horizontal level, large AC power systems need to take more advantage of FACTS technologies and HVDC lines, which can strengthen the synchronous system through electronically controlled power flows.

On vertical level, it is shown below that the segmentation is needed to allow resiliency and even immunity at the lower voltage levels, where the multitude of small consumers and potentially new prosumers are placed.

It is proposed therefore a bottom-up system segmentation, to allow the independent functionality of microsystems, usually organized as microgrids, to be developed on purpose as resilient architectures at several levels: a) at the prosumer level through local energy routers and hybrid AC and DC topologies; b) at the building level by extending the prosumer principles and c) on LV neighbourhood level, by using separations through solid-state (or static) transformers (SST) and large distributed storage.

The paper presents examples of architectures for such vertically system segmentation and provides rationale, technology readiness assessment and overview of power systems functionality advantages in this paradigm.

Moreover, a vertically segmented grid is shown to keep advantages of large synchronous systems, such as access to big energy markets, while it better enables the high penetration of renewables towards a 100% CO₂ free electricity production and use.

Figure 7 shows the basic principle of segmentation between MV and LV, by using solid state transformers which allow that each microgrid can act independently from main system, formed by Sys_1-HV and Sys_1-MV networks.

Solid state transformers are promising equipment for the future grids, thus having lately more and more practical attraction in studies ([11][12][13]), while showing also better opportunities due to technological advancements in power electronics [14].

The independent microgrids separated from main system by the solid state transformer, each microgrid with its own frequency (fm1 .. fmx) control, gives through the SST an excellent opportunity to add DC grids outputs and DC storage, on both MV and LV part.

This first type of segmentation enables the possibility to have an independent functionality of the microgrid, if proper resources are also placed in the microgrid. In fact, in order to reduce influence from the main grid, the microgrid need to be able to self-control the production and consumption in any situation: with or without energy contribution from the main grid.

Fig. 7. Vertical segmentation by using MV/LV static transformer

In Fig. 8, the DC storage on MV part brings a certain resiliency on a MV-DC network which can start growing when still having as operational the classic (and legacy) AC network. The DC storage on LV part of the static transformer has double role: a) to help grid forming on AC LV network, as previously described and b) to ensure resiliency on the new LV-DC network (labelled as “New DC microgrid”, which can be developed in time, in parallel with the LV AC microgrid).

Fig. 8. Adding storage resources associated to the MV/LV static transformer

The static transformer is a highly useful new device which improves in the same time the grid resiliency by vertically segmenting the main grid and which unleashes valuable new technologies such as AC microgrids and DC distribution.

The segmentation from Figures 7 and 8 can be even more enhanced in terms of flexibility and inter-balancing of energy production and consumption by adding, where necessary, back-to-back connectors or DC lines with AC terminals to connect the AC LV networks, as per Fig. 9. Each microgrid control remains independent, with different possible microgrid frequencies, as synthesized by the grid former of each

microgrid. The vertical and horizontal segmentation at LV level allow complete local energy ecosystems, protected from main system but also connected through precise control of the DC connections (bars or lines).

Fig. 9. Hybrid country or regional power systems

The high volume of power electronics for low voltage, needed for connecting renewables but also for the electrical vehicles needs (for both batteries and for their electrical motors), are important and objective drivers which enable such segmented AC systems at LV as well as the hybridization with DC LV microgrids.

Figure 10 gives an architectural view of the grid segmentation inside the prosumer internal network. The AC loads can remain still powered directly by the AC microgrid, however, new bidirectional AC to DC and backwards devices can separate a resilient DC bus where prosumer related resources such as PV production and storage can be efficiently connected on a resilient DC bar. Such “hybrid” inverters which provide one AC connection in the prosumer microgrid for both PV and storage already exist on market, however the use of the resilient DC network is not yet mainstream.

Fig. 10. Prosumer hybrid architecture

Figure 11 gives an additional architectural option, where the prosumer becomes connected to AC microgrid only for consuming energy for its internal grid (only an AC to DC connection, mono-directional) [15].

In this setup, the loads which still need AC supply will be connected to an DC to AC inverter which is supplying directly the legacy loads.

Fig. 11. Prosumer acting as a load-only connection on AC side

As the DC bus can be made resilient, the whole set of loads of the prosumer can be resilient as well, as all are finally supplied from the prosumer’s DC bus. To be considered that local excess of energy may be balanced through a local DC microgrid which connect the prosumers independently of the AC grid connection, as per figure 12.

The local DC microgrid can be one developed for a new building or can be the DC LV microgrid developed around the MV/LV static transformer introduced before.

Fig. 12. Prosumer additional connection to a neighbourhood of prosumers DC microgrid

The two levels of vertical segmentation – MV to LV connection through ST and hybrid inverters to connect AC microgrid to a prosumer DC bus are essential architectural improvements for a large power system.

The main drawback of the unique synchronous power system, as possibly being capable to propagate disturbances to the entire system, is proposed then to be mitigated by the vertical segmentation by separating from synchronicity the AC LV microgrids as well as the prosumer internal network, while also developing DC microgrids, through a hybridization of the today AC network. This situation shows that the “war of currents” started at the end of 19th century between the DC solution of Thomas Edison and the AC solution of Nikola Tesla has a new challenge at the beginning of 21st century.

For closing the metaphor of Titanic case, Figure 13 gives a new view of how Titanic might have been designed to be both horizontally and vertically segmented.

Segmented hybrid network Higher resiliency to disturbances

Fig. 13. The new architecture of a resilient Titantic

The similitude with voltage levels of the energy grid are also suggested in the picture. With such an architecture, the well know ship may have better mitigate large system disturbances, as it is also suggested for the power systems. The “one system for one big community” still can remain, while local resilience and self-sufficiency add additional benefits for the society supplied by such systems.

V. CONCLUSION

The paper presents in brief large power systems architectures and their solutions to enhance controllability and power flow as needed. Besides the many advantages of such large systems, it is pointed the fact that seldom disturbances may propagate in cascades over the entire system, sometimes in an unpredictable way, thus affecting the entire system, which becomes more exposed to such situations.

In order to mitigate a) the need for unique power system as cohesion of big nations or big unions of nations within single markets of energy, with b) the need for protecting the end-user from high-level disturbances (lower probability but high impact), it is considered an architecture which ensures an additional vertical segmentation of the system, enabling local microgrids, with both AC and DC (hybrid) solutions. The solution enables also into the microgrid the prosumers, both entities being able to have high resiliency, while still being non-synchronously connected to the main grid, with all advantages related to this, such as access to big markets and access to energy which is temporary not available locally from own resources.

Future work will detail more the engineering challenges of the segmented networks, in the framework of already existing conceptual efforts [16] for microgrids development.

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